

**REVIEW ON THE RESEARCH PAPER WRITTEN BY RAJKUMAR BERA
“DECOLONIZATION OF MIND IN AMITAV GHOSH’S WRITING: A POSTCOLONIAL
STUDY OF THE SHADOW LINES” PUBLISHED IN IJOHNM VOLUME III ISSUE II
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In this research paper, Mr. Rajkumar Bera tried to shed the light on feeling of nationality, decolonization and globalization through the work of Amitav Ghosh’s “A Postcolonial study of the shadow lines”. It’s a work which depicts the blurring borderlines between East and West, their religious beliefs and castes. The world without boundaries isn’t an easy task that too without bloodshed, communal riots and sufferings of the communities.

The term nationalism and nation are enigmatic and perplexing. According to Mr. Bera, “*The terms nation and nationalism despite their common usage, have always been enigmatic terms. The proliferation of theories like post-colonialism, multiculturalism, globalization and postmodernism have upheld or defied national identities and boundaries. We are living in the tempestuous uncertainties where on one hand the world is becoming footloose. The question of avoiding nations and nationalism and shifting fixed identities are finding an echo in contemporary literature.*”

The term Nationalism is a doctrine of popular sovereignty. The people must be free and liberated from any external constraints, limitations and checks. All individuals must possess their houses and must have been the masters of their houses and belongings. All should determine their paths and destiny without any pressure. All should have equal cultural, social and legal rights. The Amitav Ghosh’s shadow Lines focuses on the anonymous narrator’s family, which lives in Calcutta (now Kolkata) and Dhaka (now in Bangladesh) and their connection with an English family in London. Through his two characters, Amitav describes conflicts of nationalism and migrant cosmopolitan. This conflict is shown between narrator’s grandmother and her estranged sister’s granddaughter.

According to Mr. Bera, *The Shadow Lines* is an extreme examples of the tendency of crossing of frontiers which includes nationality culture and language barriers. This novel emphasizes on the lines we draw between people and their nation. This is actually the foundation stone of discrimination resulting in extreme violence.

Mr. Bera's research seems successful in bringing out the issues of this boundary discrimination, fearfulness among communities and the effects of communal violence. While you read the research paper you find it impressive as the usage of adjectives and punctuations. Grammatically it is well written and expressed the thoughts remarkably.

Through this novel, the writer explained the conviction shattered when the character returns to her birthplace in Dhaka after many years. She could not digest the dividing distinction between India and East Pakistan while flying over by plane. She was heartbroken when she had to fill the word Dhaka in the immigration form. She was in dilemma that though the boundaries are divided how could she divide her brain and mind into two halves which are full of memories.

In this research, according to Mr. Bera, *"The decolonized people, with all their complexities and traumas, caused by the extreme colonial rule, can never meet the colonizer on equal terms. The colonized people try to associate with the colonizer to boost their own ego and try to embrace their world, which seems to them not only glamorous but places them above the common natives. With the emergence of the new nation-states, the colonized show a tendency to forget the colonial past. They try to upgrade their sense of nationalism by reviving their native culture. The desire to forget the past in the postcolonial era is symptomatic of the colonized people's need to make a new start and to erase the painful memories of colonial subordination"*.

According to Mr. Bera, *The Shadow Lines* has a unique and supreme position in the postcolonial literature that discovered the hybridity of postcolonial nationality and migration.

Conclusion: This research paper is well-researched, fairly well written document. Mr. Bera handled the research sensitively and brought out the feelings expressed by the actual writer in his novel. By reading the paper one can easily connect and relate to the pains felt by the sufferers of the partition and the lovers of one nation and nationalism. This thesis is written in a good manner with good grammar and well written content.

WORK CITED

1. Bera, RAJKUMAR. " Decolonization of Mind in Amitav Ghosh's Writing: A Postcolonial Study of The Shadow Lines." *IJOHMN (International Journal online of Humanities)* [Online], 3.2 (2017): n. pag. Web. 24 August. 2018